

Path2Integrity feedback sheet

Instructions

During this feedback sheet, we kindly ask you to respond to the following 11 statements about the learning programme.

The survey is designed to be additive to other evaluation instruments which should be compared with each other. This requires a code generated by you, which will be anonymised by us before analysing the data, so that no conclusions can be drawn about your person. We do not collect or store your IP addresses.

In order to compare these data with those of other parts of the evaluation, we kindly like to ask you to create an identification code. This code is only used for the assignment and will be made anonymous before the analysis of the data. For this, we kindly ask you to write down the following 8-digit code:

1. Two letters that you agree upon as a group and each of you writes down (e.g. **XX**)
2. The first two letters of the city where you were born (e.g. **Hamburg = Ha**)
3. How many older brothers you have (e.g. **0**)
4. The last two letters of the birth name of your mother, your female caregiver, or the person that comes closest to being a mother for you (e.g. **Smith = th**)
5. the second letter of your eye-colour (regarding your ID-card) (e.g. brown = **r**).

Which learning unit did you just attend? (If you are unsure, please ask your instructor)

For every statement below, please tick the smiley face that best fits your experience.

	:~))	:~)	:~	:~(:~((
I am satisfied with the learning units as a whole.					
I could follow the structure of the learning units easily.					
I understood the tasks in the learning units clearly.					
I found the length of the learning units appropriate.					
I could express my opinion freely in the group.					
I was able to contribute something to the group.					
I felt the training was adequately instructed.					
I was encouraged by the trainer to participate actively.					
I have learned something useful.					
I could connect the training with my everyday life.					
I would recommend the training.					

How would you improve the training for future participants?

